

The Sanctuary of the Egyptian Gods in Dion

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An extra muros sanctuary with excellent preservation in regard to its architectural members, its sculptures, and its inscriptions. It is situated in proximity to other sanctuaries, particularly those of Demeter and of Zeus Hypsistos. It is also situated near the south fortification wall of the city. The river Baphyras flows close by, nowadays on the sanctuary's west side. The river has changed its flow several times since the construction of the Hellenistic city of Dion. The previous riverbeds were definitely on the east of the Isis sanctuary, but it is still unknown precisely at what distance. The buildings of the sanctuary of Isis surround a central court that has an altar in the center and four temples on the west side. The principal temple was built on a high podium and was accessible through five marble stairs. Two porticos stretch on the north and the south side, one on each side, with auxiliary spaces and rooms, both for the visitors of the sanctuary and for the priests, while the main entrance is situated on the east side. Most of the buildings have been dated to the Severian period. The excavations also revealed previous Hellenistic phases of construction under the central temple of the sanctuary. The sanctuary revealed a large number of sculptures, both statues, and reliefs, during its excavations. In total, the 19 sculptures, seven of which are inscribed reliefs, cover a broad chronological range from the Hellenistic times to the third century CE. Among these sculptures, there are representations of Greek divine figures, such as Aphrodite, Artemis and Poseidon. Finally, the sanctuary's inscriptions belong to two categories; they either are votive reliefs dedicated to the Isiac gods or come from the bases of statues, among which we read once more the names of Aphrodite, Artemis and Poseidon.

Date Range: 200 BCE - 300 CE

Region: Dion

Region tags: Europe, Greece, Macedonia

The city of Dion lies in the Pierian valley, on the eastern foothills of Mount Olympus. A characteristic feature of the area is the rich springs that form a floatable river, Baphyras, which flows towards the sea. Nowadays, the ancient city distances from the sea 6 km, but this distance was just 1.5 km in antiquity. The city was sacred in Macedonia. Since the fifth century BCE, its importance is highlighted when king Archelaus inaugurated the city games to honor Zeus Olympios. In addition, it was the place where important victories of both Philip II and his son, Alexander, were celebrated. In 1978 a new unknown extra muros sanctuary was brought to light. It laid near the south fortification wall of the city and not far from the already identified sanctuary of Demeter. The presence of a sacred place in the area was already known since 1951 when a trencher was used to open a new channel that would move the riverbed a few meters on the west. During this work, which destroyed parts of the western edge of the

sanctuary's precinct, marble architectural members, plinths, and sherds were brought to light. These findings were the first evidence of an ancient building at the place, but it was only the excavation that started in 1978 that revealed the sanctuary. Due to the water that covered the sanctuary the stratigraphy study was almost impossible, which, consequently, has created severe problems in the study and the understanding of the evolution of the sanctuary through the centuries.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Giuman, M. 1999. "Metamorfosi di una dea: da Artemide ad Iside in un santuario di Dion." *Ostraka* 8: 427-446.
- Source 2: Pandermalis, D. 1982. "Ein neues Helgikum in Dion." *Archäologischer Anzeiger* 97: 727-735.
- Source 3: Pandermalis, D. 1984. "Οι επιγραφές του Δίου." In *Πρακτικά του Ή Διεθνούς Συνεδρίου Ελληνικής και Λατινικής επιγραφικής*, Αθήνα, 3-9 Οκτωβρίου 1982, edited by Athina Kalogeropoulou, 271-277. Αθήνα: Υπουργείο Πολιτισμού και Επιστημών.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: [http://dion-excavation.web.auth.gr/-/](http://dion-excavation.web.auth.gr/)
- Source 1 Description: Official site of the University excavation
- Source 2 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=981
- Source 2 Description: Official site of the Ministry of Culture
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.archaiologia.gr/blog/issue/%CE%B4%CE%AF%CE%BF%CE%BD-%CF%84%CE%BF-%CE%B9%CE%B5%CF%81%CF%8C-%CF%84%CE%B7%CF%82-%CE%AF%CF%83%CE%B9%CE%B4%CE%B1%CF%82/>
- Source 3 Description: Online article

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: The excavation was conducted by the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1978- late '80s

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: University Excavation of Dion

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The sanctuary was built in proximity to the river Baphyras that created important problems during the excavations. When the excavation started, the building's floor was almost two meters underwater while the buildings were covered in more than four meters of mud due to a draining project in the area in 1951. It is crucial to note that before 1951 the water flowed on the eastern part of the sanctuary, and the draining project of the area changed the riverbed, which now flows on its west side. A small comment on the myth related to the river: this river was known in antiquity as a river connected to Orpheus. The myth says that the women living in the region around Mount Olympus' foothills killed him due to their rage for his capacity to enchant humans and nature with his music. After killing him, they washed their hands to the river Helikon. The river, ashamed, disappeared from the earth and reappeared only in Dion, carrying a different name. In contrast to the darkness surrounding Helikon, Baphyras is a sacred river, where the Nymphs appear and whose waters are used in different cultic activities, like the one of Isis.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary is part of the extra muros sanctuaries of Dion, close, though, to the city walls.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Except for the other sanctuaries, there were baths but also the Hellenistic and Roman theatres, all outside the city walls.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Baphyras was a floatable river. It is not known where the port would be.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

A single structure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

One single feature

– Other [specify]: A complex of buildings with a water channel

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ A group of features:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The buildings of the sanctuary of Isis surround a central court that has an altar in the center and four temples on the west side. Two porticos stretch on the north and the south side, one on each side, with auxiliary spaces and rooms, both for the visitors of the sanctuary and for the priests, while the main entrance is situated on the east side. Most of the buildings have been dated to the Severian period. The excavations also revealed previous Hellenistic phases of construction under the central temple of the sanctuary.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Worship:

–Other [specify]: Both

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary was built in the Hellenistic times and then structures were added until the end of the 3rd century CE.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals, the city, or the authorities contributed in offering more spaces to the sanctuary or modifying the existing ones through the centuries.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

–Other [specify]: An earthquake at the end of the fourth century was the cause of many destructions in the sanctuary.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

–Other [specify]: Earthquake

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: Only some small work during its restoration and preservation.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: To Isis, Serapis, Hermanubis and other members of the Isiac family.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Isis, Serapis, Anubis, Hermanubis, Harpocrates, Apis, Aphrodite

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Groups:

– Other [specify]: Some structures are dedicated by certain families living in the city.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The dedications, mainly marble slabs with inscriptions show the the people thanked the gods for helping them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Two of the small shrines of the sanctuary had basins of water on the floor which either arrived through an underground system of water tanks and conduits or welled up from the bottom of the basin as there are a lot of natural springs in the area.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The principal temple, situated in the center of the temenos, was built on a high podium and was accessible through five marble stairs. It was bigger than the other shrines and in a prominent position.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Earth

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Sand

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Clay

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Plaster

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Wood

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: According to the excavator, there is a Hellenistic relief that was part of the façade of the Severan temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The small shrines contained statues of Aphrodite, Eros, Isis Tyche. Outside the temples and near the altar statues of other gods were found: a head of Serapis, two Apis bulls, a statue of Artemis, a statue of Poseidon, a statue of Demeter, heads of women perhaps representing Isis.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The only statue that was still in situ in the northern portico was a female statue of Ίουλία Φρουγιανή Αλεξάνδρα, as the inscription attests. It is possible that she- and her family- had a role in the upkeep of the cult and the exhibition of this important role in the form of a statue was an act of homage and a manifestation of piety.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Apis is represented as a bull. Also, a small relief with a cockerel was found in the northern temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Floral motifs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions, mainly dedications of the devoted, were part of the decoration of the sanctuary.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: It cannot be defined with certainty which of the statues were the cult statues and which were dedicated by the devoted to the sanctuary.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Isis, Serapis, Aphrodite, Demeter, Poseidon

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: Statue of Ίουλία Φρουγιανή Αλεξάνδρα

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Relief representing Isis with her characteristic drapery with the Isiac knot on the right shoulder of her chest and the horns and the solar disk that crowns the scepter that she holds in her left hand.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Apis as a bull.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Isis, Serapis, Poseidon, Artemis, Aphrodite, Demeter.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Humans

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Human narratives

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The god Apis is present in the form of a bull.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: People dedicate to the gods in order to ask for help or to thank the gods for their successful intervention.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: The excavator believed that one of the rooms of the portico was used for incubation activities.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Not only through religious specialists.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: The cult statue would be inside the shrine.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: In certain occasions it would be probable

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Offerings of food:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: Usually poultry was offered to the Egyptian gods but there is not evidence coming from the sanctuary of Dion.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Sacred objects:

– Yes [specify]: It is something common but no evidence comes from the sanctuary of Dion.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Daily life objects:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Usually in the Graeco-Roman world poultry was dedicated to the Isiac deities. This is something, though, that depends on the social status and other animals were also sacrificed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there human sacrifices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Usually there are also valuable objects but no evidence comes from Dion.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is it required:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The sanctuary has a Hellenistic phase but the was reconstructed during the Severan period. Inscriptions also commemorate the help of citizens to the reconstruction or construction of specific spaces.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: There are some dedications in the sanctuary that represent footprints. Some researchers have related these dedications with the footprints of the devoted that would arrive at the sanctuary for pilgrimage.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Birth

– Yes

Notes: Isis is called Lochia in the sanctuary, protector of women giving birth. Some of the dedications in the sanctuary have been related to this attribute of the goddess.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Death

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: The research has not revealed a specific place which would usually have benches alongside the walls for baquets.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: There is no evidence of festivals from the sanctuary of Dion but it is likely that the festivals attested in the nearby cities, such as the Navigium Isidis, would also take place in the city of Dion.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: yearly

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

– Only initiates

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sometimes probably yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: There is no direct evidence coming from the archaeological data from the sanctuary.

Comparing with analogous sites in the region, we would expect rituals such as dressing, adorning, and cleaning the cult statues or preparing the processions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Present full time

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Some processions and festivities needed more officials taking different roles.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Notes: There are officials of both Greek and Roman names.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 300 CE

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